

Navigating TechCentral's Startup Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

James Baker, Hughie Flannery, Shihong Nie, Cassandra Song, and Yinjia Xu
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Team

James Baker, Hughie Flannery, Shihong Nie, Cassandra Song, and Yinjia Xu

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Subject Coordination

Assoc. Prof Martin Bliemel

Course Director (Diploma in Innovation)

Director, Research

UTS: TD School

Yara Vasina

Tutor, 94663 Navigating Ecosystems

UTS: TD School

Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

Contents

Foreword	3
Methodology	3
Acknowledgements	3
1 Evolution of the Sydney Startup Ecosystem	5
2 Ecosystem Mapping	6
2.1 Current Ecosystems	7
3 Leverage Proposal	7
3.1 Why & What	7
3.1.1 Vision of the state of EE in the next 10 years	7
4 Lever 1: Levering TechCentral with universities to increase talent base	8
4.1 Who, How, When	8
5 Lever 2: Levering BlueChilli's SheStarts program to be actively involved in TechCentral	9
5.1 Opportunities and fragmentations in the current EE	9
5.2 HOW & WHEN: Specific levers (actions for improvements) for change in the EE	9
5.3 WHO: Potential activators (stakeholders) who can "pull" those levers and their interconnections	10
6 Lever 3: Creating an scale-up initiative	10
6.1 Who	10
6.2 How & When	11
7 Value of the proposal	11
7.1 Lever 1	11
7.2 Lever 2	11
7.3 Lever 3	11
References	12

1 Evolution of the Sydney Startup Ecosystem

The startup scene in Sydney has evolved and seen substantial growth in the past five years. Mainly, the growth has been spurred by the increasing number of accelerators, incubators, coworking spaces, and startup events (StartupBlink, 2020). One of the most significant stakeholders which accelerated growth within the Startup ecosystem was the Sydney startup hub which was funded by the NSW government as a \$35 million investment (Investment NSW, 2021). It was Australia's first innovation center of its kind and the largest innovation center in the Southern Hemisphere (Investment NSW, 2021). Furthermore, it was and still is home to accelerators and co-working spaces such as Fishburners, Stone & Chalk, Tank Stream Labs, The Studio, and Antler Australia. It ran community and event spaces as well as a Regional Landing Pad.

Furthermore, Fishburners was established in 2011 and was one of Australia's first start-up spaces (Investment NSW, 2021). Since opening, they've had over 1,927 members and have hosted over 3,345 events that have supported over 100,000 entrepreneurs. Then, in 2013 the Westmead alliance was formed with a commitment to developing a future vision for the precinct. The establishment of the Westmead Health and Innovation District (including Parramatta North) is making a significant impact on the entrepreneurial ecosystem, advancing new industries in health, education, and innovation, accelerating future employment, and striving to become a world-class health and innovation campus through the proposed new school-enterprise campus (PriceWaterhouseCoopers, 2013). In 2015, Western Sydney University pioneered LaunchPad, an incubator for startups and SMEs with Parramatta as one of its two locations. Sydney, New South Wales is the entrepreneurial capital of Australia, and Sydney has 4 main technology districts.

In more recent years, our ecosystem has seen a rapid development in terms of members, co-working spaces and recognition in public and financial media. Entrepreneurship and the startup industry has grown over the last few years to become a significant contributor to the Australian economy, with 64% of all startups originating or basing themselves in Sydney (NSW Government, 2020). PriceWaterhouseCoopers even recognised the startup industry as a potential significant contributor to the Australian economy in a 2013 Report (PwC, 2013), predicting a contribution of \$109 billion by 2033.

As years have passed and more recognition has been given to the startup industry, the number of members and stakeholders involved has increased. More individuals and organisations on a government and corporate level have invested finances and grants, as well as opened up to utilise members from the ecosystem in their day-to-day functions. A level of collaboration and communication between the ecosystem has developed over time to form a strong bond between the stakeholders, involving a number of key industries such as transport, health, technology, infrastructure, government and the private sector.

Australian technology startups are among the most exciting and dynamic in the world, according to current statistics, with approximately 800 having been established in the country (Fintech Au, 2021). Globally, Australia ranks sixth in terms of fintech market size and investment, according to the World Economic Forum, with Sydney ranking first in Australia and 36th worldwide. (Startupblink, 2021) Australian companies are considering locating their headquarters in the Asia Pacific region, which has been identified as one of the world's fastest growing ecosystems due to the country's proximity to the region.

Australian fintech startups will gradually expand into international markets and form partnerships with foreign fintech companies in order to discover new ways to provide financial services to their customers and to broaden their product offerings, while also diversifying their offerings. Corporations such as Atlassian, one of the most successful Sydney startups, which is known for developing key product platforms and applications, expanding its core offering, and marketing and selling its own enterprise software solutions, were founded by Scott Farquhar and Mike Cannon Brooks in 2002 and have gone on to become global leaders in their fields. The company, which counts NASA and Twitter among its clients, has raised a total of \$210 million to date, with one of its investors, Atlas Partners, contributing to the total (Appendix 1).

2 Ecosystem Mapping

Entrepreneurial ecosystems are like the oceans; they are different across the globe and contain multiple relationships between organisms and nature. This is why we are focusing on the specific ecosystem that is the Sydney startup industry.

Ecosystem mapping is also a useful tool for visualizing your company's products and the systems, processes, and data flows around them. By mapping an organization's ecosystem, it is possible to get a comprehensive view of all key players, organizations, activities, etc., interact with stakeholders and raise awareness, identify existing strengths, improve gaps, and slowly form a stronger innovation ecosystem that will drive startups to grow by leaps and bounds.

2.1 Current Ecosystems

Several accelerators and incubators, such as Muru-D and BlueChilli, are now able to provide startups with early-stage funding, technology intellectual property, and expertise, allowing them to quickly transform their ideas into viable business models. As a result of these initiatives, more people are able to pursue their dreams of entrepreneurship. At the same time, an increasing number of co-working spaces and gas pedals are being established to assist in the development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem. The increasing number of startup conferences in the city is also a good indicator of the development of the startup ecosystem in the city. Encouragement of technology startups in Sydney, as well as an increase in the density of the startup ecosystem, will result in the creation of more jobs and the expansion of the city's economy. Businesses can thrive in a strong ecosystem that provides them with readily available technology, entrepreneurial education, infrastructure, and funding networks. The entrepreneurial ecosystem model, as illustrated in Appendix 2, necessitates six pillars: policy, finance, culture, support services, human capital, and markets. These pillars are interconnected, and the conditions and characteristics of each environment will combine to form a distinct ecosystem. Educational institutions, universities, and entrepreneurs can provide them with skill developmental training. Support from administrative and public institutions will make it easier and faster for startups to access banks or private financing to promote entrepreneurial activity, build a good reputation for entrepreneurs, and access their services and resources. And to establish a market network of entrepreneurs in order to obtain feedback from the first customers who test the product.

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 Why & What

3.1.1 Vision of the state of EE in the next 10 years

The Sydney startup ecosystem is expected to see immense growth over the next 10 years due to the creation of Techcentral and growing need for the expansion of technology. Through our research we established that in the future there is a need to increase University collaboration with startups to increase homegrown talent base. We further discovered that in the future the startup ecosystem will slowly be more diverse in relation to gender as well as Indigenous participation. Furthermore, we recognised that in the future there needs to be an initiative that will mentor and guide startups to scaleup growth as there is currently a gap within the ecosystem.

Through conducting an interview with Yi Ho, the Principal Precinct planner of Techcentral, he stated how "In about 10 years time, we won't see techcentral growth just a little bit. We want to see Textcentral become one of the most growing leading Innovation Districts where Start-up and scale-ups can do their best work. We are not necessarily saying that it will only be tech. We're looking through several key Industries that will be good for Techcentral like AI quantum computing, Deeptech, Biotech and creative industries." This demonstrates his assurance in his belief that the development of Techcentral will

significantly impact Sydney's startup ecosystem as it will be the leading hub for growing startups and scale-ups. He further stated how in the future a "key challenge is ensuring the diversity agenda" as a priority in Techcentral's space. He recognises that in order for Techcentral to become a diverse and socially responsible space, we need to establish an inclusive culture in the present.

Whilst interviewing Matthew Proft, he stated how in the future "it will be about which startups or scaleups apply statistics and results to solving problems efficiently, utilising technology. For me it's less about some of the sort of industry verticals and the way that will be applied to technology horizontals to solve those problems. It's the way we're using big data, the way we're using AI, the way we're embedding quantum computing solutions to solve the really big challenges in, whatever the vertical is whether it's just a ability infrastructure held you name it it's about the way we're bringing this new wave technology wave technology to address those challenges. Thus, this highlights the prediction that the utilisation of technology will be extremely important in the future. The future will be reliant on how people use the technology and ways they can create real life-changing solutions. The focus on innovation and critical thinking will be needed within the future, especially considering the increase of automating jobs.

Digital Health Executive and Growth & Innovation Leader, Phil Offer stated in an email interview we conducted that he was "optimistic that the start up ecosystem will grow in 10 years. One of the benefits of COVID19 in Australia is a more attractive destination for skilled technology talent to migrate to and retain existing people. We have an excellent university research base to provide new ideas which are not being harnessed to the maximum effect." This illustrates positivity for the future and the growth of the startup ecosystem through the increase of tech talent and the participation of uni talent.

4 Lever 1: Levering TechCentral with universities to increase talent base

4.1 Who, How, When

The first lever proposed in this report to assist with the success of Tech Central is the implementation of Government incentives. In March 2021, the Australian Federal Government announced a new incentive program to help with startups and their funding. We have identified through research and interviews with Yi Ho and Mathew Proft that there are currently no incentives to encourage University students to get involved with Sydney's emerging startup scene.

Through an interview with Mathew Proft, he concluded there is quote "a lack of talent in the Sydney startup industry so there is a strong need to grow the talent base within the Sydney startup scene through STEM Students." He stated that the majority of skill sets and jobs in this industry will be from graduate students. Whilst there are existing incentive alternatives, nothing targets University graduates. The initiative was the CSIRO Kick-Start program which provides matched funding for start-ups and small to medium enterprises to help access CSIRO's research expertise and capabilities to help grow a start-up.(CSIRO Kick-Start | business.gov.au, 2021) This is a fantastic initiative by the Federal Government but is still very limited in the amount offered in funding as funding is only matched up to \$50,000(CSIRO Kick-Start | business.gov.au, 2021), as well as being very niche in what will be funded.

The New South Wales Government currently has a website dedicated to helping anyone who is looking at starting a start-up, the website states " We are committed to embracing new ideas and harnessing innovation to deliver the next age of economic prosperity in our state."(Support for startups, 2021) but currently, the NSW government isn't offering a wide variety of incentives to draw people to the Startup industry. The NSW website currently shows what incentives are offered for start-ups and they are currently; Minimum Viable Product (MVP) grants for pre-revenue technology startups to help them engage with a potential business customer (up to \$25,000), Building Partnerships grants help revenue- generating startups and small to medium enterprises (SMEs) scale or grow by acquiring a key customer or channel to market (up to \$100,000), Regional startups fund which gives access a stipend to help with travel costs and find out about your local innovation network (up to \$2,000), and finally, The Western Sydney Investment Attraction Fund which will assist innovative businesses unlocking new jobs in Western Sydney (still in final stages). (Support for startups, 2021)

These incentives are a fantastic initiative by the NSW government but are still very limited in what start-ups will be funded. The proposed lever is for the government to implement a number of incentives. These

include; Interest-free loans, Tax exemption periods, new funding packages, access to NSW facilities, and finally competitions for university students. By the NSW government investing in incentives like the ones proposed it would allow start-ups to focus on getting their business off the ground rather than a financial burden. Furthermore, by granting access to facilities for example the health care industry it would allow start-ups the use of technology that they might not necessarily be able to afford.

To achieve these goals would require the design of new NSW incentive packages through stakeholders such as the NSW Premier Gladys Berejiklin, Dominic Perrott the Treasurer for NSW, Karen Andrews who is the Minister for Industry, Science and Technology. Additionally, to these stakeholders, it would be evident that Prime Minister Scott Morrison and federal treasurer Josh Frydenberg would have input into these initiatives as the proposed include tax breaks and interest-free loans. The final aspect of this lever is for the NSW Government to offer competitions for university students whom are studying degrees such as Honours of Entrepreneurship which is a degree currently offered at UTS. The prize could consist of 12 months of free rent at Tech Central and a small funding package to turn their hypothetical start-ups into real ones. By offering a competition to students such as the ones mentioned it provides some security in the means of students already doing research into their chosen market, along with necessary skills to successfully run a start-up and finally more motivation for young local entrepreneurs. The proposed lever plays a crucial role not just in the success of Ecosystems such as Sydney Start-up Hub and Tech Central but also in increasing the number of start-ups and jobs generated in NSW.

5 Lever 2: Levering BlueChilli's SheStarts program to be actively involved in TechCentral

5.1 Opportunities and fragmentations in the current EE

Since Techcentral has not been yet created, this is the best opportunity to determine the culture of the building first hand in the beginning stages of its development to cater for the future. We have the power to create a vibrant inclusive community within the tech space for the sake of increasing innovation and that all voices are heard. "Inclusive companies are 1.7 times more innovative" (Martic, 2019). Through research, it was found that in the "startup ecosystem- where the most innovative, high potential businesses of the future are being created- women remain grossly under-represented". It has been further identified that "women represent 24% of start-up founders" (Genome, 2017). This demonstrates the fragmentation of the disparate lack of female startups within the tech community. Matthew Proft even stated how "I feel like there's more work that needs to be done" in relation to creating more diversity within the tech ecosystem, with Yi Ho corroborating this view by saying that the "diversity agenda" is a "key challenge" as "we need to figure out how to actually engage these people more". This reinforces the need for initiatives that allow for increased gender diversity as it is a fragment within the ecosystem.

Furthermore, covid has also influenced women significantly as it has resulted in women not being able to focus on their startup due to having to perform domestic tasks and child caring. Thus, we can use the creation of Techcentral as an opportunity to diversify the tech startup ecosystem as it has the ability to increase female startups and entrepreneurs. This would be done through the lever which will be further discussed below.

5.2 HOW & WHEN: Specific levers (actions for improvements) for change in the EE

The lever would be to create a connection and coupling between the stakeholders at Techcentral and the Bluechilli's SheStarts program. We would leverage the SheStarts program to be involved in Techcentral. The SheStarts program is a competitive startup program designed to fund 10 female entrepreneurs who are launching technology startups. It consists of a boot camp where they work with mentors and entrepreneurs within the field to develop their ideas.

At the end of the program, the chosen 10 founders receive a \$100,000 investment and a place in their accelerator program. This collaboration between the two organisations would ensure there is a focus of female startups within the culture of Techcentral. This would take the form of allowing the SheStarts

program to hold its events and bootcamp within Techcentral and hold bigger networking functions for female entrepreneurs. This would be beneficial as currently, the SheStarts program floats from coworking spaces and doesn't have an assigned working space, thus by moving into one building it can be more centralised. In addition to this lever, we leverage Techcentral to create a diversity council to make sure they are accelerating their D&I targets and to create a culture of equal opportunity between male and female employees.

5.3 WHO: Potential activators (stakeholders) who can “pull” those levers and their interconnections

It has been found that “to improve gender equality in tech and entrepreneurship, we need to design for it” (Hazelle, 2017). To initiate that, Michelle Long, the Associate Director of Sydney Startup Hub, would be a potential activator who would be able to collaborate directly with BlueChillis SheStart's program and bring that program into the Techcentral space. Having had a history and passion for increasing female entrepreneurship in the startup ecosystem, Long has been involved in the Tech Ready Women program which helped 100 women go through a pre accelerated program to mentor and help kickstart their startups. She has identified 3 key values that women need to create a startup which include networking, confidence and access to capital, thus she will be able to use this knowledge and experience to help the development of Techcentral. Further collaboration would be with Matthew Proft, the director of Techcentral who would need to work with the Filipia C. Araujo, the director of the SheStarts program, to put this into action. Through conducting an interview with him, he stated how “It's more than just working with a female founders program, it's actually embedded the mindset of diversity as a priority in what we do”. Therefore, in addition to partnering with SheStarts we also leverage Techcentral to create a diversity council to ensure that diversity is top priority in setting an inclusive space. This would be used to monitor and analyse Techcentral's level of inclusivity to ensure that all employees have equal opportunities regardless of gender. The council would be involved in the hiring process and foresee the goal setting processes of the space. Not only would the diversity council be focused on women, but it would also deal with the inclusivity of Indigenous participation to make Techcentral a welcoming place. This reinforces Proft's view that it will take an “open approach to make it open and welcoming to Indiegenuous, LGBTQ+ and female participants”. This further corroborates with Hazelle's study where “Those who play a role in supporting startups must ensure their programmes are designed to attract, include and support female founder's” (Hazelle, 2017). This is exactly what this collaboration would do in “creating spaces for women to learn about the opportunities available, develop key skills, identify in themselves the potential for leading globally scalable companies, and see in others examples of how it can be done” (Hazelle, 2017).

6 Lever 3: Creating an scale-up initiative

6.1 Who

In order for the startup ecosystem to develop, a number of changes should be made that will enable for a more diverse industry in terms of investment and output of innovative ideas. The majority of startups require financial investment in order to progress from a startup to a scale-up and functioning business, with the development of MVPs towards a viable product and business operations (Miller Cole, 2019). One of the key difficulties in this industry is startups failing to understand the responsibilities and tasks to becoming a scale-up, mostly due to a lack of resources, skilled staff and financial sustenance (Harnish, 2020). While some private sector firms invest in startups that are aligned to their own industry or future ambitions, there are still a large number of startups who fail in the first few years due to lack of investment. In our research and our interview with Matthew Proft, Director of TechCentral, we've identified the need in the next 10 years for there to be a shift in the level of guidance and education that startups receive in order to grow into scale-ups, as there is the potential to lose innovative ideas and technology that has been developed due to failure in this progression.

Government and policy makers have recently been heavily involved in the startup industry, promoting the importance and growth of business and technology development across our ecosystem. TechCentral provides a clear impression of the direction and position that the startup and innovation industries will have in the long-term growth of Sydney and our ecosystem.

6.2 How & When

We are proposing the development of a mentorship and guidance program, named “From Start to Scale” that is available to all startups. The program will educate and guide them through the key steps to evolving into a scale-up. The current ecosystem has a heavy pool of resources available to both startups and scale-ups separately. However, there is a lack of guidance and direction provided to businesses between these two stages, resulting in a high level of business failure. These start/scale-ups are developing innovative technologies in areas such as AI, healthtech, cyber security, infrastructure and sustainability that have the potential to radically change our economy and ecosystem. Many of these potential technologies and solutions are being lost due to the number of startups failing to transition successfully into scale-ups.

This program would involve key stakeholders including Government funding and grants, volunteer private sector executives and previous successful entrepreneurs to form a mentorship group that startups and entrepreneurs can access along the journey of building their business. Based out of the many startup hubs dotted throughout our ecosystem, the program will involve 1-on1 sessions, seminars and group discussions to allow for a flexible and intimate learning environment. The program will teach important items such as how to manage costs, attain funding and investment, accessing resources and sourcing skilled labour in order to continue progressively developing their ideas and businesses into a scale-up model.

While this will be a volunteer run program, and require some Government funding to maintain, the return for the mentors and stakeholders is that they will receive direct and early access to potential investment opportunities for these innovative technologies as well as a tight-knit ecosystem. Collaboration, communication and consistent support are the three key goals of this strategy that we propose, and as a result will see a higher number of successful startups who offset their technologies and developments for the ecosystem’s benefit. There is also the addition of many new skilled, experienced and educated members into the startup and entrepreneurial ecosystem, where information and ideas can be shared to all members.

7 Value of the proposal

7.1 Lever 1

By offering a competition to students such as the ones mentioned it provides some security in the means of students already doing research into their chosen market, along with necessary skills to successfully run a start-up and finally more motivation for young local entrepreneurs. The proposed lever plays a crucial role not just in the success of Ecosystems such as Sydney Start-up Hub and Tech Central but also in increasing the number of start-ups and jobs generated in NSW.

7.2 Lever 2

Advantages of this collaboration would be increased gender equality and directly shows the company’s involvement in tackling this social issue within the workforce. Not only will it provide Techcentral with a good reputation, it has also been proved that “inclusive companies are 120% more likely to hit financial goals” (Reiners, 2020) with “companies with equal men and women earning 41% higher revenue” (Reiners, 2020). Thus, not just the employees benefit from a more diverse workforce with more opportunities, but also the company itself will benefit financially in the long term.

7.3 Lever 3

Collaboration, communication and consistent support are the three key goals of this strategy that we propose, and as a result will see a higher number of successful startups who offset their technologies and developments for the ecosystem’s benefit. There is also the addition of many new skilled, experienced and educated members into the startup and entrepreneurial ecosystem, where information and ideas can be shared to all members. The overall benefit for the stakeholders’ participation in this level and by joining the ecosystem is the increased potential for financial and networking gain. Their names and organisations will become key leaders for start-ups, scale-ups and other firms alike across both their own industry as well as the start-up industry in terms of visibility. There is also the likelihood of recognising potential investment opportunities, new network connections and collaboration opportunities that aren’t public yet or well-known among competitors.

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